

ULTRASONIC RECONSOLIDATION AT 20 KHZ - A POTENTIAL REPAIR APPROACH FOR AEROSPACE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Recycling of end-of-use (EoU) aerospace composites and manufacturing waste has gained traction over the past decade. Conventional methods such as shredding, pyrolysis, and solvolysis are widely used, with recovery rates of 10–75% of the original mechanical performance. However, these methods often compromise value-retention factors such as fiber length, orientation, and component geometry, limiting their reuse in high-performance applications. A circular approach is therefore necessary—one that emphasizes the damage-free separation and reuse of continuous fiber-reinforced layers. Effective reuse requires either rebonding the separated layers to restore the original laminate structure or employing them as reinforcing patches in structural repairs. Recent research has demonstrated the viability of ultrasonic-assisted separation and reconsolidation to recover and reprocess carbon and glass fiber composites. In carbon fiber-reinforced PEEK systems, optimizing ultrasonic reconsolidation through Design of Experiments (DoE) has shown improvements in mechanical performance. Reconsolidation time and force—primarily governed by the temperature profile—define the process window. Hold time and holding force influence thermal characteristics and laminate integrity. Exceeding optimal holding force by 25% leads to fiber-matrix debonding and cohesive failure. When carefully controlled, ultrasonic reconsolidation provides a viable pathway for structural reuse and material circularity in thermoplastic composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced composites are favored in aerospace and aeronautical applications due to their high strength-to-weight ratio. Carbon fiber composites, in particular, offer several advantages over traditional materials, including excellent fatigue resistance, enhanced fire and corrosion resistance, the ability to integrate functions, and flexibility in producing complex geometries [1]. These materials can be up to four times lighter than steel while maintaining comparable performance [2]. Additionally, they contribute to sustainable mobility by lowering CO₂ emissions by up to 20% during their operational life due to lightweighting [3]. However, a growing concern in the aerospace sector is the increasing volume of composite waste generated during production and at end-of-use (EoU). In line with the European Waste Directive, such waste must be managed through a hierarchy that prioritizes reduction, reuse, recycling, recovery, and finally, landfill [4]. Recycling composites remains challenging due to their complex mix of fibers, resins, and fillers, especially with thermoset matrices [5-7]. Common industrial

recycling methods like pyrolysis and solvolysis often degrade material quality [8, 9]. Therefore, recovery methods enabling reuse in high-performance applications are essential [4].

Thermoplastic composites (TPCs) offer significant advantages over thermoset composites, particularly in reparability, due to their ability to be reheated above their glass-transition (amorphous) or melting temperature (semi-crystalline). This thermal reversibility enables efficient joining and repair processes such as ultrasonic welding (USW), which has been increasingly recognized as a promising method for TPC repair. Compared to conventional fusion-based techniques like arc or resistance welding, USW offers several benefits including short cycle time, localized heating, reduced energy consumption, and high automation potential [10, 11]. USW relies on mechanical vibrations to generate heat through friction and viscoelastic dissipation at the interface, often facilitated by energy directors (EDs) in the form of thin films or meshes [12, 13]. Furthermore, successful spot welding without EDs has also been demonstrated [14, 15]. Recent advances demonstrate the growing potential of USW as a viable repair technique for TPCs. Li and Palardy reported high recovery rates (86–94.5%) in mechanical performance using USW with nanocomposite ED films across multiple repair cycles, outperforming resistance heating methods in terms of consistency and bond strength [16]. The thermoplastic matrix not only ensures strong mechanical integrity and chemical resistance but also allows repeated processing, making it ideal for sustainable repair strategies. Despite requiring more complex repair methods compared to thermosets, techniques like USW, induction, and resistance heating have shown proven effectiveness for restoring delaminated and damaged TPC structures in aerospace applications [17-19].

While ultrasonic welding (USW) is well-established for joining aerospace-grade thermoplastic composites, its application in repair remains underexplored. This study introduces our novel ultrasonic reconsolidation approach for repairing separated, multi-directional CF-PEEK laminates without energy directors. Using statistical design of experiments, optimal USW parameters were identified based on lap-shear strength. Repair quality was further assessed via 3D X-ray microscopy and temperature analysis during the post-reconsolidation phase. The influence of holding force and time on thermal behavior was analyzed in-depth. Additionally, successive repairs were evaluated through mechanical testing and microstructural analysis, highlighting ultrasonic reconsolidation as a promising alternative to conventional aerospace repair techniques.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Thermoplastic composite laminate

Figure 1a illustrates the cross-ply thermoplastic carbon fiber (CF)-PEEK (poly-ether-ether-ketone) composite laminate examined in this study. The laminate, commercially known as CETEX-TC1200, was supplied by Toray Advanced Composites (Nijverdal, Netherlands). PEEK, a high-performance semi-crystalline thermoplastic from the polyaryletherketone (PAEK) family, exhibits exceptional mechanical strength and chemical resistance. With a glass transition temperature of 143 °C and a high melting point of 343 °C, it is well-suited for demanding aerospace and advanced medical applications. Ultrasonic C-scan inspections confirmed the laminate was free from critical manufacturing defects such as voids or delaminations. Table 1 presents the material properties of the CF-PEEK laminate as specified by the manufacturer. The laminate was fabricated with a cross-ply layup of alternating 0° and 90° fiber orientations, resulting in a final consolidated thickness of 2.48 ± 0.03 mm. Test specimens, each measuring 110 mm in length and 30 mm in width, were precision-cut from the laminate using micro water-jet cutting at Fraunhofer IWM (Freiburg, Germany), as shown in Figure 1a. The corresponding cross-sectional micrograph is presented in Figure 1c. Layer separation was achieved using a hybrid process that combined ultrasonic-assisted pre-cracking at 20 kHz [20] with mechanical delamination via a custom-built peel-off apparatus [21–23], as depicted in Figure 1b. The resulting top and bottom layer thicknesses were measured at 1.03 ± 0.05 mm and 1.74 ± 0.04 mm, respectively. The thickness of the top layer reflects the minimum achievable limit of the ultrasonic pre-cracking technique.

Figure 1: (a) CF-PEEK specimen with dimensions used for the investigation (b) Separated CF-PEEK layers and (c) Cross-sectional view of CF-PEEK specimen with 0° and 90° fiber orientation [24].

Material properties	Units	Values
Fabric type	–	5-Harness satin weave
Laminate layup	–	[0/90/0/90] _s
Number of plies	–	8
Cured ply thickness	[mm]	0.31
Area weight	[g/m ²]	0.0051
Glass transition temperature (T _G)	[°C]	140
Melting point (T _M)	[°C]	337
Decomposition temperature (T _D)	[°C]	>550
Ultimate tensile strength 1-direction	[MPa]	776
Young's Modulus E ₁₁ direction	[GPa]	56.1

Table 1: Material properties of CF-PEEK laminate. The table has been already published in [24].

2.2 Ultrasonic reconsolidation of CF-PEEK at 20 kHz

Ultrasonic repair experiments were conducted using a HiQ 20-6200 ultrasonic plastic welding system from Herrmann Ultraschalltechnik GmbH (Karlsbad, Germany), equipped with a 6.2 kW generator. A schematic of the setup is shown in Figure 2a. The resonance unit included a piezoelectric converter, quick-change adapter, a 1:2 booster, and a rectangular sonotrode (75 mm × 35 mm) capable of delivering a maximum amplitude of 49 μm. The converter transformed electrical energy into mechanical vibrations at a resonance frequency of 20 ± 0.5 kHz. These vibrations were transmitted through the booster to the sonotrode and applied to the joining interface under ambient conditions. Temperature monitoring at the repair interface was performed using thermocouples. Three independent experiments were conducted to record interface temperatures during reconsolidation and post-reconsolidation. A control PC triggered data acquisition via the generator, with temperature data collected through a LabVIEW interface. The separated CF-PEEK layers were joined in a single lap-joint configuration with a 35 mm overlap length and 30 mm width, as shown in Figure 3b. The thicker layers served as the bottom adherend, while thinner layers were placed on top. Prior to welding, the bonding surfaces were cleaned with ethanol to remove contaminants, and the samples were securely clamped using toggle clamps (Figure 3c). The ultrasonic reconsolidation process window was determined using a statistical design of experiment using a non-linear statistical “Central Composite Circumscribed” (CCC) model from the software MODDE [25].

Figure 2: (a) Schematic representation of the ultrasonic repair setup with the oscillation unit. (b) Enlarged view of the clamping system at the reconsolidation zone and (c) actual setup of ultrasonic repair. Figure taken from [26].

2.3 Mechanical and microstructural characterization

The reconsolidated CF-PEEK lap-joint specimens were mechanically tested to determine their ultimate lap-shear strength using a universal testing system of type Z020 from Zwick/Roell (Ulm, Germany) with a 20 kN load cell. Tests were conducted under monotonic loading at a constant displacement rate of 2 mm/min, with the thin layer positioned on top and the thick layer at the bottom, aligned along the loading axis. Surface observations after post-failure were carried out using a Smart Zoom-5 light microscope (Zeiss, Oberkochen, Germany). Additionally, fracture surface analysis was performed using SEM (Zeiss EVO-15) to examine fiber and matrix behavior after repeated reconsolidation trials. Cross-sectional analysis on the repaired zone was not feasible as the repaired joints failed during the specimen preparation. Hence, a Zeiss Xradia Versa 520 system from Fraunhofer IAF (Freiburg, Germany) was used for the 3D X-ray microscopy (XRM) analysis on the repaired CF-PEEK samples.

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3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Identification of suitable ultrasonic reconsolidation process window

Ultrasonic repair experiments were conducted on CF-PEEK laminates to optimize process parameters and evaluate tensile lap-shear strength (F_{UTS}) performance. Surface plots were generated by varying two ultrasonic welding parameters while holding one constant: weld time t_{US} (750 ms), weld force F_{US} (601 N), and oscillation amplitude u ($37.9 \mu\text{m}$) as illustrated in Figure 3a-c. The resulting F_{UTS} values were approximately $15.65 \pm 1.31 \text{ kN}$, $15.48 \pm 1.78 \text{ kN}$, and $15.78 \pm 1.45 \text{ kN}$, respectively. These results were validated through six additional trials, yielding an average lap-shear force of $15.61 \pm 1.73 \text{ kN}$. In all cases, the tensile lap-shear force increased initially with weld time and force before decreasing, likely due to fiber bundle damage from excessive polymer squeeze-out. To prevent thermal degradation of the PEEK matrix, weld parameters were capped to ensure peak temperatures remained near $550 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, below the decomposition threshold. The optimal process condition was identified at $F_{US} = 600 \text{ N}$, $t_{US} = 750 \text{ ms}$, and $u = 37 \mu\text{m}$, yielding a consistent F_{UTS} of 15.6 kN .

Figure 3: 3D surface plots of CCC model plotted for (a) constant reconsolidation time $t_{US} = 750 \text{ ms}$, (b) constant reconsolidation force $F_{US} = 601 \text{ N}$, (c) constant oscillation amplitude $u = 37.9 \mu\text{m}$. Figure adapted from [26].

Figure 4a shows the temperature measurements during ultrasonic repair revealed that oscillation amplitude significantly influences thermal behavior, whereas weld force has minimal impact. The highest temperatures recorded were $547.4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $559.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for the recommended parameter triple and the optimizer function, respectively. A marginal increase in amplitude by $0.9 \mu\text{m}$ resulted in a $12 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ rise in temperature, highlighting its critical role in thermal input. In contrast, variations in weld force showed negligible influence on peak temperature. When oscillation amplitude increased, temperatures exceeded the decomposition threshold, emphasizing the need for careful amplitude control. Differential scanning calorimetry revealed localized changes in crystallinity, although no significant impact on macroscopic properties was detected. Figure 4b shows the representative load-displacement curves during the tensile lap-shear test. Six repetitions have been performed for the determined suitable ultrasonic reconsolidation parameter and the average lap-shear force was found to be $15.6 \pm 1.3 \text{ kN}$.

Figure 4: (a) Representative time-temperature curve for the determined suitable ultrasonic reconsolidation process parameter and (b) shows the representative load-displacement curve from the tensile lap shear test of the reconsolidated CF-PEEK laminates. Figure adapted from [26].

3.2 Temperature behavior and failure analysis during post-reconsolidation of CF-PEEK under varying holding forces and hold times

Temperature being a characteristic variable during USW influences the quality of joint performance based on ultrasonic process parameters. This section investigates the influence of holding force and hold time on the temperature distribution and microstructural behavior during the post-reconsolidation phase of ultrasonic welding in thermoplastic composites. Temperature measurements at four distinct locations (T1–T4) across the weld zone revealed spatial variation in thermal behavior, which directly influenced matrix diffusion and defect formation. The parameters used for the characterization of post-reconsolidation phase is listed in Table 2.

Oscillation Amplitude u [μm]	Reconsolidation force F_{US} [N]	Reconsolidation time t_{US} [ms]	Holding force F_H [N]	Hold time t_H [s]
37	600	750	0	0
			700	2
			750	4
			800	5
			900	6

Table 2: Parameters used for ultrasonic reconsolidation experiments. The table has been already published in [24].

At a holding force of 700 N and a hold time of 2 s, temperature gradients were evident, with T1 and T2 showing 28% higher temperatures than T3 and T4. This non-uniformity suggested inconsistent residual polymer distribution, resulting in localized decomposition and pore formation (50–200 μm) due to incomplete matrix diffusion. Increasing the hold time to 4 s improved thermal uniformity and matrix diffusion, as reflected by fewer defects and better adhesion (see Figure 5a (i and ii)). At 6 s, the temperature disparity between sensors further decreased to 8%, and failure analysis showed hardened matrix improved consolidation. For a higher holding force of 800 N at 2 s, temperatures were 6% lower than those recorded at 700 N due to enhanced heat dissipation. However, despite higher pressure, insufficient hold time still led to poor matrix diffusion, though the pore size reduced to 5–50 μm . Extending the hold time to 4 s reduced temperature variation and enhanced polymer diffusion (see Figure 5b (i and ii)). At 6 s, thermal distribution became more uniform and matrix diffusion improved, with minor fiber dislocations likely caused by processing or mechanical testing. At 900 N, temperature measurements followed similar trends, though T1 data were unavailable. T2 consistently recorded higher

values than T3 and T4, but the overall temperature was 5–10% lower compared to lower forces. At 2 s, minimal porosity was observed, but significant fiber-matrix squeeze-out occurred, attributed to high compressive forces acting on the laminate before full diffusion. With increased hold time (4 s and 6 s), uniform cooling was achieved (see Figure 5a (i)), but excessive pressure led to cohesive failures within the fiber bundles and even fiber breakage, indicating over-consolidation and shear-induced damage (see Figure 5a (ii) [24]).

Experiments without applying holding force or hold time demonstrated a slower cooling rate. After 8 s, the temperatures at T1 and T2 remained near the glass transition temperature (T_G) of PEEK, while T3 and T4 were below T_G . Although the matrix had melted during ultrasonic reconsolidation, diffusion between fiber bundles was insufficient, leading to ductile failure of the residual matrix during mechanical testing due to inadequate solidification [24]. These results emphasize the critical role of optimized holding force and duration in achieving uniform thermal distribution, effective matrix diffusion, and defect-free welds. Short hold times, regardless of applied pressure, are insufficient for complete diffusion and defect mitigation. Conversely, excessive holding force applied for extended durations can lead to matrix squeeze-out and fiber damage. A balanced combination of force and time is therefore essential to ensure effective reconsolidation and mechanical integrity of the joint.

Figure 5: Temperature response during the post-reconsolidation phase, and the micrograph of the welded zone after tensile lap-shear test for (a) $F_H = 700$ N; $t_H = 4$ s, (b) $F_H = 800$ N; $t_H = 4$ s and (c) $F_H = 900$ N; $t_H = 4$ s. Figure adapted from [24].

3.3 Quality of ultrasonic reconsolidation of CF-PEEK after successive reconsolidation cycles

The mechanical performance of ultrasonically reconsolidated CF-PEEK joints was evaluated over three successive repair cycles using optimized process parameters: a holding force of 750 N and a hold time of 5 seconds. The first cycle corresponded to the initial reconsolidation following layer separation, with two additional repair cycles subsequently applied. A progressive reduction in lap-shear strength was observed with each cycle. The initial reconsolidation yielded an average lap-shear load of 15.65 ± 1.02 kN, whereas the third cycle showed a significant decline to 10.3 ± 1.5 kN, representing an approximate 35% reduction in joint strength. A representative load-displacement response revealed a drop in both load capacity and nominal displacement, with the displacement decreasing from 2.4 mm in the first cycle to 1.18 mm in later cycles [24]. The decrease in mechanical performance is attributed to surface degradation of the PEEK matrix. Repeated exposure to high temperatures during ultrasonic processing can induce thermo-oxidative degradation, forming a surface layer that inhibits effective reconsolidation, similar to observation in [27]. Although the core remains intact, the damaged surface layer likely limits matrix flow and interfacial bonding. Consequently, residual polymer accumulation with increasingly amorphous character was observed on the failure surfaces, leading to brittle failure

behavior in the later repair cycles.

Figure 6: (a) Maximum tensile lap-shear force for 3-cycle repair of separated CF-PEEK layers by ultrasonic reconsolidation. (b) Representative load curve of a single specimen at each repair cycle tested with a displacement velocity of 2 mm/min. Figure taken from [24].

3.4 Ex-situ characterization of CF-PEEK by 3D X-Ray Microscopy (XRM)

3D-XRM scans were conducted on the repaired region within a volume of 5 mm × 5 mm, highlighted by the blue box. In a two-dimensional perspective, the scans encompass the reconsolidated interface (represented by the purple-shaded area) along with the top and bottom neighboring CF-PEEK layers (refer Figure 7a). Figure 7b shows the XRM scan in yz plane for the pre-determined ultrasonic reconsolidation process parameter which revealed void content upto 0.99% and poor interfacial contact near the weld line, attributed to uneven residual polymer distribution caused by material ejection during layer separation. This led to fiber-matrix debonding and cohesive failures above the weld interface. Additionally, fiber layer decohesion was observed near the weld zone. In contrast, specimens repaired using optimized reconsolidation and post-reconsolidation parameters exhibited significantly reduced voids (0.71%) and debonding, with no cohesive failures detected (see Figure 7c). These results confirm the effectiveness of optimized holding force and hold time time in enhancing interfacial bonding and maintaining structural integrity in the repaired CF-PEEK laminates [24].

Figure 7: (a) Schematic of the CF-PEEK specimen with the identified optimal parameter scanned using 3D XRM. (b) 3D-XRM scan in yz plane for the (b) determined suitable reconsolidation parameter and for the (c) determined reconsolidation and post-reconsolidation parameter. Figure adapted from [26].

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Ultrasonic repair of CF-PEEK laminates demonstrated that process parameters—particularly oscillation amplitude, weld force, and weld time significantly influence joint performance and thermal behavior. Optimal ultrasonic reconsolidation conditions ($F_{US} = 600$ N, $t_{US} = 750$ ms, $u = 37$ μ m) consistently yielded high lap-shear strengths (approx. 15.6 ± 1.3 kN) without exceeding the thermal degradation threshold of the PEEK matrix. Oscillation amplitude had the most pronounced effect on peak temperature, underscoring its critical role in thermal control during welding.

Post-reconsolidation analysis revealed that both holding force and hold time are essential for ensuring uniform thermal distribution and effective matrix diffusion. Inadequate hold time led to poor diffusion and porosity, while excessive holding force induced fiber damage and cohesive failure. A balanced condition (e.g., 750 N, 5 s) achieved optimal consolidation, minimizing voids and defects. Spatial temperature gradients across the weld zone further emphasized the need for controlled thermal management to avoid localized degradation.

Repeated ultrasonic repair cycles under optimized parameters showed a gradual decline in mechanical strength (approximately 35% after three cycles), primarily due to surface degradation and thermo-oxidative damage of the PEEK matrix. This led to reduced interfacial bonding and a shift toward brittle failure modes.

3D-XRM scans confirmed that poor reconsolidation parameters resulted in interfacial voids and fiber-matrix debonding, while optimized conditions improved bonding quality and reduced internal defects. Overall, the study demonstrates that precise control of ultrasonic and post-weld parameters is critical to ensure high-quality, repeatable repairs in CF-PEEK laminates, while repeated thermal exposure imposes limitations on long-term repairability.

5 OUTLOOK

To close the loop, alternative ways for the reconsolidation include bulk processing methods such as hot pressing are available. Therefore, a feasibility study has been carried out to assess this as an alternative to ultrasound-based reconsolidation. Hence, laminates consisting of polypropylene (PP) as a matrix and glass fibers (GF) as reinforcing fibers were cut in strips with the same process as described above and arranged in two layers in a shear edge mold. This dual layer was then reconsolidated into a single laminate in a Vogt Labopress P200S type hydraulic press at a consolidation temperature of 180°C and a pressure of 5 bar for 20 minutes. The consolidated composite laminates were then investigated by means of X-ray analysis on a Baker & Hughes Phoenix nanotom M X-ray Computed Tomography (CT) system and observation of a plastographic specimen with a Keyence 7000 optical microscope respectively. The plastographic specimen is prepared by sequentially grinding a 50 mm specimen with a cylindrical geometry (which contains a small section of the laminate embedded in an epoxy) with grit papers from coarse (320 grit for 4 minutes) to fine grain size (500, 800 and 1200 grit for 2 minutes each) on Silicon Carbide foils, followed by polishing with diamond pastes (9 micron for 3.5 minutes and 3 micron for 2.5 minutes) on a felt pad. The grinding and polishing are completed on a Streurs Tegramin-25 machine, with a continuous flow of water to clean the debris.

The laminate was segmented in a total of 720 slices in the due process of a scan that was conducted at an X-ray tube voltage of 100 kV and power of 12 W, which ran for 1500 ms. The 3D reconstruction of the laminate from CT-scan (Figure 8a) shows a consolidated PP-GF laminate, with minimal misalignments in the fiber bundle orientations and consistent bundle volumes. Furthermore, a highly regular mesostructure can be observed across major part of the Y-Z cross section (Figure 8b) of the laminate. The tows, or fiber bundles, are evenly sized and regularly spaced relative to each other. The exact cause for a section with spatially distorted fiber bundles (observed towards right hand end in Figure

8b, enclosed within the white dotted square) is likely a gap between the strips. The plastographic inspection of the X-Z plane (Figure 8c) further confirms the mesostructural observations from the CT-scan. Additionally, a homogenous distribution of fibers within the bundles can be clearly observed. Furthermore, lack of any noticeable voids or defects confirms adequate consolidation of the laminate.

The evident regularity in the fiber distribution and a high degree of accuracy in the bundle characteristics at meso- and micro-levels, as well as a seemingly uniform quality of consolidation attest to the potential of hot pressing as an alternate reconsolidation route. Nevertheless, gaps during stacking have to be prevented as they may lead to fiber misorientation. Finally, the single strips recovered via ultrasound might not only be used for repair of existing laminates but might also serve as a basis for reuse of recycled bulk materials without significant loss of material integrity.

Figure 8: (a) 3D reconstruction of a PP/GF laminate consolidated with a hot press at 180°C, 5 bar for 20 minutes (b) Section of the consolidated PP/GF laminate in Y-Z plane showing mostly uniform fiber bundle (or tow) characteristics – except at gaps in between the single strips (enclosed within dotted white square). Some of the transverse fiber bundles are marked with the dotted black line (c) Plastograph of a representative section of the PP/GF laminate demonstrating regular intra-bundle fiber distribution as also nearly no defects and minimal resin-rich areas.

The evident regularity in the fiber distribution and a high degree of accuracy in the bundle orientation at a meso-level, as well as a seemingly uniform quality of consolidation attest to the potential of hot pressing as an alternate reconsolidation route. Nevertheless, gaps during stacking have to be prevented as they may lead to fiber misorientation. Finally, the single strips recovered via ultrasound might not only be used for repair of existing laminates but might also serve as a basis for reuse of recycled bulk materials without significant loss of material integrity.

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